

Perception of Family Medicine Residents on the Use of Small Group Discussion in Comparison to Standard Lectures

Ahmed Mohammed Gharawi ,
Ghada Alarfaj ,
Alaa Alahmari
*Family and community Medicine Dept, Prince Sultan Military Medical City,
Riyadh, Saudi Arabia*

Abstract

Background: Effective teaching methods are essential in medical education to ensure that residents acquire the necessary knowledge and skills. Traditional lecture-based learning has been a mainstay in family medicine (FM) residency programs. However, small group discussions have been proposed as a more engaging and effective alternative.

Objective: This cross-sectional study aims to compare the perceptions of FM residents regarding the use of small group discussions versus standard lectures during weekly academic day activities.

Methods: A structured questionnaire was administered to all FM residents at Prince Sultan Military Medical City (PSMMC), Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. The questionnaire assessed perceptions of engagement, knowledge retention, and overall satisfaction with both teaching methods. Descriptive statistics and chi-square tests were used to analyze the data. Qualitative responses were analyzed thematically.

Results: Of the 90 residents, 79 completed the questionnaire, resulting in an 87.7% response rate. The majority of participants agreed that small group discussions are a better approach to learning compared to standard lectures. The study's regression analysis further supported the preference for SGD, with significant coefficients indicating a strong relationship between the perceived quality and effectiveness of SGD and residents' preference for this method ($\beta = 0.611$, $p < 0.001$). Qualitative analysis showed the emergence of 5 themes based on the questions on the interviews.

Conclusion: FM residents perceive small group discussions as more engaging and effective for knowledge retention compared to standard lectures. These findings suggest that incorporating more small group discussions into the curriculum could enhance the educational experience and learning outcomes for residents.

Keywords: FM residents, small group discussions, Standard lectures, Perceptions.

Suggested citation: Gharawi, A.M., Alateeq, A.M., Alarfaj, G., Afify, A., Albatal, S., Alahmari, A., & Kofi, M. Perception of Family Medicine Residents on the Use of Small Group Discussion in Comparison to Standard Lectures. *European Journal of Contemporary Education and E-Learning*, 2(5), 3-18. DOI: 10.59324/ejceel.2024.2(5).01

Introduction

Family Medicine is an important medical specialty that provides continuing and comprehensive care for the patient. Early screening and advice on lifestyle modification to prevent diseases from occurring is also an important task of family physicians, along with diagnosing and managing acute and chronic diseases. Understanding the duties of a family physician and learning the clinical process of diagnosing and managing diseases is an integral part of becoming a successful Family Medicine physician. MBBS graduates that join the Saudi Family Medicine residency programs acquire knowledge through different ways, but a lot of the teaching occurs during weekly academic day activities (WADA). WADA is a day in which residents are pardoned from their hospital duties so that they learn and discuss different topics weekly for educational purposes. This is usually carried out by different teaching methods. The effectiveness of teaching methods in medical education is paramount for preparing residents to meet the demands of clinical practice (Hay, et al., 2019). Traditional lecture-based teaching has been a primary approach in Family Medicine (FM) residency programs, favored for its ability to convey a substantial amount of information to a broad audience efficiently. However, this method often falls short in fostering active engagement and deep learning among residents (Ali, et al., 2021; Adesunloye, et al., 2008).

For many years, teaching has been done through the traditional standard lecture pattern, in which large groups are taught a certain topic. This way is based on providing residents a certain amount of information in a limited time. The residents are usually just listening to the new information and trying to memorize rather than discuss how to apply it clinically together, which is considered as a disadvantage (Roshni, M., & Rahim, A. (2020). Lectures given by good instructors don't necessarily mean that learning outcomes are achieved by the students (Carpenter, et al., 2013). To address these limitations, there has been an increasing interest in interactive teaching methods, such as small group discussions. These discussions are believed to enhance educational experiences by promoting active participation, critical thinking, and peer collaboration. In a small group setting, residents have the opportunity to delve deeper into topics, ask questions, and benefit from the diverse perspectives of their peers and instructors (Sartania, et al., 2022; Weyrich, et al., 2008; George, et al., 2020).

According to a study done in Qassim university, Saudi Arabia, students' perceptions of team-based learning as a teaching method were higher than standard lectures (Nawabi, Bilal, & Javed, 2021). Another study concluded that "the small group discussion was interactive, friendly, and bridged the gap between the teacher and student. The student's communication skills are also improved, making small group discussions more effective than the traditional teaching methods (Annamalai, Manivel, & Palanisamy, 2015)." Additionally, a study done on dentistry students comparing the lecture teaching method versus the small group problem focused discussion method

found out that the group with problem focused discussion obtained higher grades in comparison to those receiving lectures only, and that problem focused discussion diverts student time to more complex tasks but requires a greater commitment from the teachers (Moreno-López, et al., 2009).

Despite the potential advantages, there is a paucity of research directly comparing the effectiveness of small group discussions with traditional lectures within residency programs, including FM programs (Hashim, 2022). Understanding the perceptions of FM residents regarding these teaching methods is essential for informed curriculum development and improving educational outcomes (MacKinnon, et al., 2017; Alrashed, El Said, & Kofi, 2023).

This cross-sectional study aims to investigate the perceptions of FM residents about the use of small group discussions compared to standard lectures during their weekly academic activities. By evaluating aspects such as engagement, knowledge retention, and overall satisfaction, this study seeks to identify which method residents find more effective and the reasons behind their preferences. The insights gained can contribute to the ongoing efforts to enhance teaching strategies in medical education.

Methodology

Research Questions

- 1- What are the perceptions and experiences of Family Medicine residents regarding the use of Small Group Discussions during weekly academic day activities?
- 2- What are the reasons behind Family Medicine residents' preferences or dislikes regarding Small Group Discussions compared to standard lectures?

Study Design

This study employed an Exploratory mixed qualitative and quantitative cross-sectional research design to evaluate the perceptions of FM residents regarding the use of small group discussions versus standard lectures during their weekly academic day activities.

Settings

The study was done in the Prince Sultan Military Medical City (PSMMC) Family Medicine (FM) residency program, which is one of the largest and most well-established programs in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia with a population of 90 male and female residents of all levels (R1-R3) and more than 65 trainers. The study used PSMMC's Alwazarat Healthcare Care Center's facilities and interactive classrooms.

Participants

The study involved 79 FM residents from Prince Sultan Military Medical City (PSMMC), Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. All R1 to R3 level FM in PSMMC were asked to enroll in the study by filling out a questionnaire voluntarily.

Inclusion Criteria

- Trainees who are currently enrolled in the FM residency program at Prince Sultan Military Medical City.
- All Residents from level 1 to level 3 to capture a range of experiences.
- Both male and female residents to ensure a diverse perspective.

- Individuals who willingly consent to participate in the study and are willing to share their experiences and perceptions.

Exclusion Criteria

Individuals who do not provide informed consent to participate in the study.

- Residents who are not enrolled in the FM residency program at Prince Sultan Military Medical City.
- Residents who have completed their FM residency training and are no longer actively participating in the program.
- Exclude residents who are on extended leave or are not actively engaged in the program during the study period.

The study selected 10 participants to be included in individualized structured interviews, using a convenience sampling technique. Participants included were level 3 Residents “senior residents”, both male and female, who were exposed to small group discussion and standard lecture learning during their weekly academic day activities (WADA) over their 3 academic residency training years.

Data Collection

Instruments

The study incorporated a validated questionnaire taken from another research after the main author’s permission was granted (Nawabi, 2021).

The Questionnaire comprised of three sections:

Demographics: Gathering basic information about participants.

Perceptions of Small Group Discussions: Evaluating engagement, knowledge retention, and satisfaction.

Perceptions of Standard Lectures: Assessing the same parameters for comparison.

The questionnaire was evaluated before using it in data collection. A test of validity was applied and results are shown in table 1. The results include Pearson correlation coefficients between each statements and its dimension (quality and effectiveness) in addition to the overall axis (Preference). All the correlation coefficients were significant at less than 0.001 level. These results mean that the questionnaire has a good validity level.

Table 1. Test of Validity for Questionnaire Statements

Statement	Correlation Coefficients with Quality	Correlation Coefficients with Preference
Quality of Small Group Discussion		
I find myself more focused during Small Group Discussion activities than lectures	0.805**	0.837**
I learn better in Small Group Discussion setting	0.789**	0.817**
During standard lectures I often find myself thinking of non-related things	0.791**	0.738**
I am easily distracted during traditional lectures	0.809**	0.76**
I wish we can implement small Group discussion in every WADA during residency	0.752**	0.678**

I find that Small Group Discussion is suitable for the level of post-graduating students in their studies like residency	0.845**	0.845**
I am more likely to fall asleep during standard lecture than Small Group Discussion activities	0.782**	0.786**
	Correlation Coefficients with Effectiveness	Correlation Coefficients with Preference
Effectiveness of Small Group Discussion		
I easily remember what I learn when working in team than in lectures	0.868**	0.81**
Small Group Discussion activities are fun and I enjoy them	0.835**	0.82**
I do better in exams in topics learned through Small Group Discussion than standard lectures	0.838**	0.757**
Small Group Discussion help me improve my grade	0.863**	0.818**
I think Small Group Discussion is better approach to learning as compared to lectures	0.904**	0.903**

Note: (**) Significance at <0.001

Test of reliability is the other evaluation procedure, which can be executed using alpha Cronbach. Table 2 shows the calculated values of alpha Cronbach which should be 0.7 or above to prove an acceptable level of reliability. The values were 0.902, 0.911, and 0.946 for quality, effectiveness, and preference, respectively. These results assure a good level of reliability. The results in Tables 1 and 2 prove that the questionnaire is valid and reliable according to the data sample. This means that the applied questionnaire is a good instrument to collect the required data from the sample individuals.

Table 2. Test of Reliability for Questionnaire Dimensions and Axis

Dimension \ Axis	Cronbach Alpha
Quality of Small Group Discussion	0.902
Effectiveness of Small Group Discussion	0.911
Preference of Small Group Discussion	0.946

Procedure

An electronic questionnaire was distributed to the residents using their smartphone chat applications and their registered phone numbers, and a 10-item section composed of closed-ended questions was developed to assess perceptions of participants on a 5-point Likert-type scale (strongly disagree to strongly agree) on using small group discussion vs standard lectures during Weekly Academic Day Activity (WADA). Validation of the questionnaire was established by 2 senior educationalists and a psychometrician. Participants were informed about the study's purpose and provided with informed consent forms. The questionnaire was administered in person, allowing for immediate clarification of any questions. Responses were collected anonymously to ensure confidentiality and promote candid feedback.

The two main authors conducted individualized structured interviews in a private and comfortable setting, which included an office or a designated interview room at Alwazarat Primary Healthcare Center with the help of an audio-recording instrument

(after participants' consent) to ensure accurate data capture. One author conducted the interviews while the other author wrote his observations during the interviews to record additional notes and contextual information. A pilot-tested detailed interview guide that includes open-ended questions related to the research objectives was developed by the two main authors and used as the data collection instrument. Each interview lasted for 15-20 minutes.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical approval (letter No. HP-01-R079) was received from the Institutional Review Board of the Ethics Committee at Prince Sultan Military Medical City in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia, after ensuring confidentiality of the data related to the research and only group research members will have access on the data. Data collected for this research will not be used in other research projects. Informed consent was taken from the participant to ensure autonomy. Maintain strict confidentiality and anonymity of participants' responses. The authors and co-authors made sure to address any ethical concerns that may have arisen during any stage of the research conduction.

Data Analysis

The latest version of Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) was used for data analysis concerning the questionnaire. The differences in the measurements were analyzed. Baseline comparison was assessed using standardized difference. Descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages, mean, and standard deviation) were used to describe the categorical and quantitative variables. The statistical significance was at $p < .05$ with a Confidence Interval of 95 %.

The study adopted a thematic analysis approach. All the audio recordings of the interviews were transcribed by the first author. The second author reviewed the transcribed audio recordings twice, ensuring precise transcription of recorded content. A coding system was created to label and categorize the text by the second author. The transcripts were reviewed multiple times by the authors to look for possible themes in the interviews. Five themes were finalized after the agreement of both authors and quotes coinciding with each theme were included (Table 6).

Results

In this section, the results of descriptive analysis are shown in addition to the results of statistical tests. The descriptive data include the distribution of sample observations according to their FM residency and training activities. Their level of agreement on questionnaire statements is introduced with necessary measurements. Evaluation of the questionnaire was done via tests of validity and reliability. The relation between quality of SGD and its effectiveness was explored and estimated to clarify the importance of that approach compared to the traditional lecture approach.

Table (3) describes the distribution of respondents according to their current level of FM residency, previous experience in other residency programs, and weekly academic day activities (WADA) using the small group discussion method. From Table 3 (a), it can be shown that the distribution of respondents according to their current level of FM residency is approximately equal for the three levels with 31.6% for level 1, 32.9% for level 2, and 35.5% for level 3. The distribution of previous experience in other residency programs is described in Table 3 (b). 87.3% of respondents don't have previous experience in other residency programs, while 12.7% do have other

experience. Table 4 (c) introduces the percentage of respondents who have attended weekly academic day activities using the SGD approach. As shown in the table, 7.6% of the respondents did not attend SGD before, however the majority have attended WADA using SGD. The data in Table 1 introduces an image of the job nature and experience of family residency and small group discussion activities for the sample individuals.

Table 3. Distribution of Respondents According to a) Current Level of FM Residency, b) Previous Experience in Other Residency Programs, and c) Weekly Academic Day Activity Using Small Group Discussion Method

a) Distribution of current level of FM residency		
Level	Number of respondents	Percentage of respondents
1	25	31.6%
2	26	32.9%
3	28	35.5%
Total	79	100%
b) Distribution of previous experience in other residency programs		
Level	Number of respondents	Percentage of respondents
Yes	10	12.7%
No	69	87.3%
Total	79	100%
c) Distribution of weekly academic day activity using small group discussion approach		
Level	Number of respondents	Percentage of respondents
Yes	73	92.4%
No	6	7.6%
Total	79	100%

In Table 4, the statements of the applied questionnaire are supplied. The first seven statements measure the elements of SGD quality. These statements determine the advantages of the small group discussion (SGD) approach compared to standard lectures (SL). The other five statements measure the effectiveness of SGD when adopted during family medicine residency program activities. The axis that measure the overall preferences of the SGD approach is also introduced. The table shows the values of mean, standard deviation (S.D.), coefficient of variation (C.V.) for all statements, the two dimensions, and axis. Furthermore, Chi-square test was applied to test if there is a significant difference among the agreement scales (strongly agree, agree, natural, disagree and strongly disagree). A significant difference has been found among all the agreement levels for each statement. The means of each statement, dimension and axis with their measures of absolute and relative dispersion (S.D. and C.V.) helped to determine the agreement degree of the twelve statements, the two dimensions and the overall axis. The mean values were categorized to select the agreement degree as shown below:

- From 1 to less than 1.8 strongly disagree
- From 1.8 to less than 2.6 disagree
- From 2.6 to less than 3.4 Neutral

- From 3.4 to less than 4.2 agree
- From 4.2 to less than 5 strongly agree

Based on these categories, it was found that the agreement level was agree for eight statements in the dimensions of SGD quality and effectiveness. In addition, the overall preferences of SGD achieved an agree level. On the other hand, four statements (5, 7, 10 and 11) had a neutral level of agreement. Consequently, the results in table 4 means that the SGD method has a good level of quality and effectiveness based on the sample individuals' view and that it is preferred with a good level.

Table 4. Level of Agreement for Questionnaire Statements

Statement	Mean	S.D.	C.V. (%)	Agreement	Chi-square	P-value
1. I find myself more focused during Small Group Discussion activities than lectures	3.65	1.12	30.8%	Agree	29.29	<0.001
2. I learn better in Small Group Discussion setting	3.53	1.08	30.7%	Agree	33.22	<0.001
3. During standard lectures I often find myself thinking of non-related things	3.66	1.11	30.3%	Agree	37.77	<0.001
4. I am easily distracted during traditional lectures	3.58	1.06	29.5%	Agree	34.48	<0.001
5. I wish we could implement small Group discussions in every WADA during residency	3.30	1.20	36.4%	Neutral	12.84	0.012
6. I find that Small Group Discussion is suitable for the level of post-graduating students in their studies like residency	3.76	1.09	29.0%	Agree	34.22	<0.001
7. I am more likely to fall asleep during standard lecture than Small Group Discussion activities	3.30	1.32	40.1%	Neutral	12.33	0.015
Quality of Small Group Discussion	3.54	0.91	25.6%	Agree		
8. I easily remember what I learn when working in team than in lectures	3.54	1.02	28.9%	Agree	37.39	<0.001
9. Small Group Discussion activities are fun and I enjoy them	3.61	1.17	32.4%	Agree	22.96	<0.002
10. I do better in exams in topics learned through Small Group Discussion than standard lectures	3.29	0.99	30.1%	Neutral	30.31	<0.003
11. Small Group Discussion help me improve my grade	3.35	0.93	27.9%	Neutral	50.18	<0.004
12. I think Small Group Discussion is better approach to learning as compared to lectures	3.58	1.05	29.2%	Agree	40.81	<0.005
Effectiveness of Small Group Discussion	3.48	0.89	25.5%	Agree		
Preference of Small Group Discussion	3.51	0.87	24.8%	Agree		

To describe the relation between the quality of SGD as an independent variable and the SGD effectiveness as a dependent variable, analysis of simple linear correlation

and regression was executed. The results are provided in table 5. It can be noticed that the correlation coefficient is (0.874) with a P-value of (<0.001), which verifies the strong direct and significant correlation between quality and effectiveness of the SGD approach. Furthermore, the casualty between the two variables was studied using the simple regression model. The results of analysis indicate a significant effect of the quality on effectiveness of SGD with a coefficient of (0.611) and a P-value of (<0.001). The coefficient of determination (Adjusted R2) was (0.76), which means that 76% of the variation in effectiveness depends on the quality of SGD, and 24% of the variation depends on other factors. These results clearly explain the importance of quality elements on the effectiveness of the SGD approach, which makes it preferred by family medicine residency members.

Table 5. Results of Simple Linear Correlation and Regression between Quality and Effectiveness of Small Group Discussion

Variable	Regression Coefficient (β)	Sig.	Correlation Coefficient	Sig.
Quality of Small Group Discussion	0.611	<0.001	0.874	<0.001
Overall Significance	F= 247.9	<0.001	Adjusted R2= 0.76	

The analysis produced 5 main themes:

A knowledgeable Training Experience:

All the participants had an overall positive experience with the training program. There were many reasons that influenced their experience but some factors had more effect. The high patient exposure seen at primary healthcare centers had a big impact on their learning and confidence. The high number of patients seen made it more feasible to encounter different cases every day that improved their learning outcomes as stated in the interviews. A very important factor that also heavily influenced their training experience is the presence of valuable trainers. The majority of the residents mentioned that the trainers are good doctors that are always around for discussions and answering any questions. They stated that they are very helpful and allow as much time as needed for discussions about particular cases. Weekly academic day activities made an impact in terms of knowledge improvement because of the variety of procedures done and topics that were discussed through different teaching methods.

Understanding Small Group Discussions (SGD):

Most of the residents had a clear idea and understanding of how small group discussions are carried out appropriately. One individual stated that

“it is a flexible way of learning that allows sharing of knowledge with others.”

Some participants also mentioned that it is a way of learning that allowed for sharing of different perspectives on certain subjects. Most stated that it is usually involving a small number of individuals that discuss a certain topic. The majority stated that the number of participants in the group is usually 3-5 individuals. Participants also agreed that opinions can be discussed in the group about approaches and topics more freely, and that certain topics are better carried out using the small group discussion teaching method.

Improved Engagement and Learning Outcomes with SGD:

Many participants find small group discussions (SGD) more effective due to better understanding of topics. For example, one of the residents mentioned that discussing a topic in a small group of 3-5 individuals provides a deeper understanding and improvement in knowledge. Moreover, it also improves participation and communication skills. It allows for good communication and collaboration to search and look together for an answer when a challenge is faced. Many participants acknowledged communication about different subjects carried out during the small group discussions as an important strength. Most participants find themselves more engaged and focused with small group discussions. Enhanced concentration with small group discussions is an important point that all the participants agreed on. Reduced concentration during standard lectures was noted by some of the residents. For example,

“The concentration span in lectures is 20 minutes, then I will lose my concentration. In small group discussions I am more concentrated as there is more active learning and sharing of knowledge which is fun and informative.”

Exciting SGD versus Didactic Lectures:

Participants reported having certain feelings when attending both small group discussions and standard lectures. The majority of participants felt excited when attending small group discussions and the reason behind their excitement is that they get to share and discuss ideas directly with their colleagues. Some also report that they are motivated or encouraged to participate and share knowledge with others. For Example,

“SGD increases the engagement, understanding and your input. You’re excited and motivated to share your input on the topics with your colleagues in contrast to the old traditional lecture where you are only receiving.”

A part of the participants mentioned that they are also usually excited when attending standard lectures but it can sometimes be boring depending on the presenter and lecture.

“I feel excited when attending standard lectures most of the time but it depends on the presenter and how well he or she prepared for the topic and elicited it on the slides. If the lecture is mostly just full of text and is too long I might be a bit bored, so it is basically presenter-dependent.”

Enhancing Learning Effectiveness:

A higher preference for the small group discussion teaching format was noted by the participants, however, incorporation of both teaching methods was suggested by all. For example,

“I think we need to have both of them. The small group discussions are effective in some topics, while standard lectures are effective in other topics, usually that require a certain approach.”

Most felt the need to have more small group discussions as the standard lecture format is applied more in the curriculum. Better preparation of topics beforehand is an important point that all participants agreed on. Some even recommended allocating topics to groups earlier so that there is enough time for preparation before the discussion is initiated. Participants concur that standard lectures are presenter-dependent, so the assembling of a clear presentation that draws attention and encouragement of discussion by the presenter through either cases or questions is advised by most.

Table 6. Themes, Codes, and Illustrative Quotations Associated with Perception of FM Residents on The Use of Small Group Discussions Compared to Standard Lectures

Themes	Codes	Illustrative quotations
A knowledgeable Training Experience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High patient Exposure • Diversity of cases • Expert Trainers • Weekly topic discussions 	<p>“It is a good experience being a part of PSMMC program. We have very high exposure to patients, and sometimes we encounter stressful situations that ultimately enhance our learning of how to deal with similar situations in the future.”</p> <p>“The exposure in our main primary health care center for me is excellent because one of the benefits is exposure to many patients. Also, the variety of cases seen here increased my knowledge.”</p> <p>“The experience is very good, honestly. I got to learn a lot from the exposure to a high number of patient in our primary healthcare centers and the intelligent trainers.”</p> <p>“There are valuable trainers who are good doctors and help us a lot.”</p> <p>“I have the opportunity to discuss any of the cases I encounters with excellent trainers. I got to revise some of the medical topics and learn multiple approaches through our weekly academic day.”</p> <p>“If we focus on training, weekly academic day activities are one of the things that really improved my knowledge. Discussions were excellent.”</p> <p>“The experience depends from the junior level to the senior level. With progress in time, it became better as we learned more through our increased exposure to patients and our discussions in weekly academic day activities.”</p>
Understanding small group discussions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Group size • Exchange of knowledge, opinion, ideas 	<p>“What I understand is that small group discussions are like three to five individuals, either mix or only male or female, where we discuss cases, treatments or anything and we compare with other groups.”</p> <p>“It’s flexible learning that allows a small number of participants to discuss a topic or case.”</p> <p>“Groups of 3-5 individuals discussing a topic or subject to share ideas and get perspective from each other.”</p> <p>“What I can recall is that we are divided into 3-4 groups and each group gets to discuss a certain case or topic together.”</p>
Improved engagement and learning outcomes with SGD	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Better understanding of topics • Active participation and communication • Enhanced Concentration 	<p>“Small group discussions promote deeper understanding of topics. Small group discussions allowed for improvement in my knowledge, as well as improvement in my skills in participating in any different topic and communicating with my colleagues.”</p>

		<p>“Overall, I think small group discussion are more effective for better engagement and participation, including sharing of ideas.”</p> <p>“I find myself less engaged in lecture based. In contrast, small group concentrates more on specific points. We dig more and we share more knowledge with each other, and the engagement is higher.”</p> <p>“Communication is a strength. If we face a challenge, we collaborate and research, together. We will sometimes search for a specific point in our phone or iPad, this is happening in small group discussions, it doesn’t happen in standard lecture.”</p> <p>“I think that the issue with standard lectures is that sometimes it is just pouring a lot of knowledge into you, which can sometimes make it harder for you to concentrate. Also the engagement is usually poor. Small group discussions make you able to give your thoughts and defend it with your colleagues and also hear their points of view.”</p> <p>“The concentration span in lectures is 20 minutes, then I will lose my concentration. In small group discussions I am more concentrated as there is more active learning and sharing of knowledge which is fun and informative.”</p> <p>“In standard lectures, the concentration of the audience depends on the presenter which I consider a weakness. Also, there isn’t a lot of interaction, in contrast to SGD.”</p> <p>“with regards to standard lectures, I have a short span of concentration, definitely. I don’t necessarily get bored, but sometimes I get lost.”</p>
<p>Exciting versus lectures</p> <p>SGD versus didactic</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Excitement • Encouraged/motivated • Boring lectures 	<p>“I am always excited to attend SGD because I get to discuss anything directly with my colleagues.”</p> <p>“mostly excited and eager to share ideas with my colleagues.”</p> <p>“SGD increases the engagement and understanding and your input. You’re excited and motivated to share your input on the topics with your colleagues in contrast to the old traditional lecture where you are only receiving.”</p> <p>“I feel comfortable. I feel encouraged to engage more than in lectures, definitely, and share more knowledge, and perceive more knowledge.”</p> <p>“I feel excited when attending standard lectures most of the time but it depends on the presenter and how well he or she prepared for the topic and elicited it on the slides. If the lecture is mostly just full of text and is too long I might be a bit bored, so it is basically presenter-dependent.”</p>

		“Sometimes I might be bored if the lecture is too long and there is no interaction or cases in the lecture to make us more concentrated.”
Enhancing learning effectiveness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diversity • Preparation • Encouraging interaction 	<p>“I think we need to have both of them. The small group discussions are effective in some topics, while standard lectures are effective in other topics, usually that require a certain approach.”</p> <p>“Some topics need the old traditional lectures. Some topics, especially the new topics, new guidelines, new medications, new hypothesis or new research I think needs small group discussions.”</p> <p>“To use both teaching methods depending on the topic. To incorporate small group discussion more in the learning. And also to assign topics earlier for small group discussions so that the participants prepare well before wise.”</p> <p>“Better preparation of the topics or cases before beginning the discussion so that everyone can share knowledge at an equal level.”</p> <p>“I think that small group discussions must be incorporated more as a teaching method but with better preparation by the individuals, otherwise it will be useless.”</p> <p>“Small group discussions I feel needs better arrangement in terms of distribution and setting of the objectives and goals of the discussions. Sometimes, the question is long and inappropriate for a small group discussion, and distribution is too big for a small group so it’s hard to grasp the information.”</p> <p>“Need of better preparation of the material before a discussion or before a lecture is presented.</p> <p>“Better preparation of the topics by the presenters and to encourage discussion and participation through cases or questions”</p>

Discussion

The study's findings demonstrate that small group discussions (SGD) significantly enhance the engagement and knowledge retention of family medicine (FM) residents. The strong preference for SGD over traditional lectures, reflected in the high correlation between the perceived quality and effectiveness of SGD, highlights the need for an educational paradigm shift within residency programs. The increased focus and reduced distractions reported by residents during SGD activities suggest that this method not only improves attention but also fosters a deeper understanding of the material, as indicated by the better retention and learning outcome.

These results align with previous studies that have demonstrated the benefits of active learning techniques in medical education. A majority of the residents in our study reported that they learned better in SGD settings, highlighting the effectiveness of small-group interactions in facilitating learning. For example, a study done by Zaima

Ali, 2023 and colleagues concluded that small group discussions allowed for a more useful way of learning topics and enhancing communication and reasoning skills. Similarly, another study was done on clinicians under training by Isabel McMullen in 2013 has shown that small group learning promotes better engagement and collaboration, and better experiences among psychiatry residents. A noticeable proportion of residents in our study reported being easily distracted during lectures, with a considerable number stating they were likely to fall asleep. Similarly, a study was done on medical student by Hafezimoghadam in 2013 during a course of BLS (Basic life support) found out that students reported a significant response to likely falling asleep during standard lectures than in team-based learning activities. Our study adds to this body of evidence by specifically examining the impact of SGD within a family medicine residency context, thereby emphasizing its relevance to postgraduate medical education.

Although the results supported the preference of the residents of SGD over traditional standard lecture from the data extracted from the questionnaire, a detailed interview with senior FM residents reported the need of standard lectures for more complex long subjects for its direct simple way of teaching over the SGD.

The clear preference for SGD observed among the participants suggests that residency programs should consider integrating more SGD sessions into their curricula. This approach could not only improve educational outcomes but also enhance resident satisfaction, which is crucial for maintaining motivation and reducing burnout (West, et al., 2016). The findings also raise important considerations for educators in terms of how they structure and deliver content, emphasizing the need for interactive and collaborative learning methods.

While this study provides valuable insights, it is not without limitations. The study's sample size was relatively small and limited to a single institution, which may affect the generalizability of the findings. Additionally, the self-reported nature of the data may introduce bias, as residents might overestimate their engagement or learning outcomes. Future research should aim to include larger, more diverse samples and consider longitudinal designs to assess the long-term impact of SGD on clinical competence and patient care outcomes.

Building on these findings, further research could explore the specific elements of SGD that contribute most to its effectiveness, such as the role of facilitators, group dynamics, or the types of materials used. Additionally, investigating the impact of SGD on other aspects of resident development, such as communication skills or professional identity formation, would provide a more comprehensive understanding of its benefits.

Conclusions

In conclusion, this study highlights the substantial benefits of small group discussions in enhancing the learning experience of clinical training residents such as family medicine residents. By fostering greater engagement and improving learning outcomes, SGD offers a promising alternative to traditional lecture-based teaching methods. Given these findings, there is a strong case for incorporating more SGD sessions into residency curricula to better prepare future family physicians for the complexities and broad domain of their clinical practice.

References

- Adesunloye, B. A., Aladesanmi, O., Henriques-Forsythe, M., & Ivonye, C. (2008). The preferred learning style among residents and faculty members of an internal medicine residency program. *Journal of the National Medical Association*, *100*(2), 172–175. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0027-9684\(15\)31205-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0027-9684(15)31205-0)
- Ali, A. A. A., Nasrallah, M. S., Rashed, M. H., Ibrahim, Y. A., Rasheed, R. M., El-Meedani, H. M., Abdel-Hamid, M. S., & Mustafa, H. A. (2021). Learning style among family medicine residents, Qatar. *The Pan African medical journal*, *38*, 167. <https://doi.org/10.11604/pamj.2021.38.167.27668>
- Ali, Z., Khan, R., Gulshad, S., Mushtaq, S., Waqas, S., & Farooq, R. (2023). Lectures or small group discussions: What do undergraduate medical students perceive and prefer. *Journal of Medical Education Development*, *15*, 38-43. <https://doi.org/10.52547/edcj.15.48.38>
- Alrashed, D. A., El Said, T., & Kofi, M. A. (2023). Family medicine residents' perspectives on different teaching modalities used throughout their training. *Journal of family medicine and primary care*, *12*(7), 1291–1297. <https://doi.org/10.4103/jfmpe.jfmpe 115 23>
- Annamalai, N., Manivel, R., & Palanisamy, R. (2015). Small group discussion: Students perspectives. *International journal of applied & basic medical research*, *5*(Suppl 1), S18–S20. <https://doi.org/10.4103/2229-516X.162257>
- Carpenter, S. K., Wilford, M. M., Kornell, N., & Mullaney, K. M. (2013). Appearances can be deceiving: instructor fluency increases perceptions of learning without increasing actual learning. *Psychonomic bulletin & review*, *20*(6), 1350–1356. <https://doi.org/10.3758/s13423-013-0442-z>
- George, T., Carey, R. A. B., Abraham, O. C., Sebastian, T., & Faith, M. F. (2020). Trainee doctors in medicine prefer case-based learning compared to didactic teaching. *Journal of family medicine and primary care*, *9*(2), 580–584. <https://doi.org/10.4103/jfmpe.jfmpe 1093 19>
- Hafezimoghdam, P., Farahmand, S., Farsi, D., Zare, M., & Abbasi, S. (2013). A Comparative Study of Lecture and Discussion Methods in education of Basic Life Support and Advanced Cardiovascular Life Support for medical students. *Turkish Journal of Emergency Medicine*, *13*(2), 59–63. <https://doi.org/10.5505/1304.7361.2013.15986>
- Hashim M. J. (2022). Teaching Family Medicine and General Practice. *Korean journal of family medicine*, *43*(2), 93–100. <https://doi.org/10.4082/kjfm.20.0223>
- Hay, K., McDougal, L., Percival, V., Henry, S., Klugman, J., Wurie, H., Raven, J., Shabalala, F., Fielding-Miller, R., Dey, A., Dehingia, N., Morgan, R., Atmavilas, Y., Saggurti, N., Yore, J., Blokhina, E., Huque, R., Barasa, E., Bhan, N., Kharel, C., ... Gender Equality, Norms, and Health Steering Committee (2019). Disrupting gender norms in health systems: making the case for change. *Lancet (London, England)*, *393*(10190), 2535–2549. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(19\)30648-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(19)30648-8)
- MacKinnon, K., Marcellus, L., Rivers, J., Gordon, C., Ryan, M., & Butcher, D. (2017). Student and educator experiences of maternal-child simulation-based learning: a systematic review of qualitative evidence. *JBIC database of systematic reviews and*

implementation reports, 15(11), 2666–2706. <https://doi.org/10.11124/JBISRIR-2016-003147>

McMullen, I., Cartledge, J., Levine, R., & Iversen, A. (2013). Team-based learning for psychiatry residents: a mixed methods study. *BMC medical education*, 13, 124. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6920-13-124>

Moreno-López, L. A., Somacarrera-Pérez, M. L., Díaz-Rodríguez, M. M., Campo-Trapero, J., & Cano-Sánchez, J. (2009). Problem-based learning versus lectures: comparison of academic results and time devoted by teachers in a course on Dentistry in Special Patients. *Medicina oral, patología oral y cirugía bucal*, 14(11), e583–e587. <https://doi.org/10.4317/medoral.14.e583>

Nawabi, S., Bilal, R., & Javed, M. Q. (2021). Team-based learning versus Traditional lecture-based learning: An investigation of students' perceptions and academic achievements. *Pakistan journal of medical sciences*, 37(4), 1080–1085. <https://doi.org/10.12669/pjms.37.4.4000>

Nawabi, S.N. (2021). Students' perception about lectures and team based learning. *Pakistan Journal of Medical Sciences*. <https://doi.org/10.12669/pjms.37.4.4000>

Roshni, M., & Rahim, A. (2020). Small group discussions as an effective teaching-learning methodology for learning the principles of family medicine among 2nd-year MBBS students. *Journal of family medicine and primary care*, 9(5), 2248–2252. <https://doi.org/10.4103/jfmpc.jfmpc.1228.19>

Sartania, N., Sneddon, S., Boyle, J. G., McQuarrie, E., & de Koning, H. P. (2022). Increasing Collaborative Discussion in Case-Based Learning Improves Student Engagement and Knowledge Acquisition. *Medical science educator*, 32(5), 1055–1064. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40670-022-01614-w>

West, C. P., Dyrbye, L. N., Erwin, P. J., & Shanafelt, T. D. (2016). Interventions to prevent and reduce physician burnout: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Lancet (London, England)*, 388(10057), 2272–2281. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(16\)31279-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(16)31279-X)

Weyrich, P., Schrauth, M., Kraus, B., Habermehl, D., Netzhammer, N., Zipfel, S., Jünger, J., Riessen, R., & Nikendei, C. (2008). Undergraduate technical skills training guided by student tutors--analysis of tutors' attitudes, tutees' acceptance and learning progress in an innovative teaching model. *BMC medical education*, 8, 18. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6920-8-18>

